

Benzothiazole Derivatives: Part IV. Synthesis of some 2- and 6-(1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-yl) benzothiazoles and 2- and 6-(1,3,4-Thiadiazol-2-yl) benzothiazoles as Potential Antiinflammatory Agents

S. N. SAWHNEY, JANVIJAY SINGH and O. P. BANSAL

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra

Manuscript received 16 April 1974; accepted 12 August 1974

A number of compounds belonging to the series 2- and 6-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles and 2- and 6-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles have been synthesized by the cyclodehydration of 1-(2- and 6-benzothiazolecarbonyl)-2-acylhydrazines with polyphosphoric acid and by the treatment of these diacylhydrazines with phosphorus pentasulphide respectively with a view to testing their antiinflammatory activity.

THE non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs have currently assumed considerable importance due to the undesirable side effects observed in glucocorticoids used to reduce or inhibit inflammation¹. Some 2- and 6-(4-thiazolyl)benzothiazoles and 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)benzothiazoles synthesised in our laboratory were found to approach phenylbutazone in their antiinflammatory action in mice². As these are new types of structures possessing antiinflammatory activity, the role of different moieties in this respect is not yet clearly understood. It was, therefore, decided to explore the effect of substituting some five membered N and S or O containing heterocyclic systems other than thiazole in the benzothiazole nucleus. In this communication, we report the synthesis of some compounds belonging to four series, namely, 2-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles (I, X = O), 2-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles (I, X = S), 6-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles (II, X = O) and 6-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles (II, X = S) with a view to testing their antiinflammatory activity. Three 2-trifluoromethyl analogues of II (X = O) were also prepared as this group is known to enhance antiinflammatory activity in some *N*-phenylanthranilic acids³.

I
X = O or S
R = Alkyl or Aryl

II
X = O or S
R = Aryl; R' = H or CF₃

These series of compounds were obtained by the reaction sequences A and B given in the Scheme I below :

6-benzothiazolecarboxylic acid prepared by the hydrolysis of ethyl ester (VI, R' = CF₃) which in its turn was obtained by treating ethyl 4-amino-3-mercapto-

SCHEME 1

benzoate⁴ (V) with trifluoroacetic anhydride in *N,N*-dimethylaniline.

Selected compounds from each series were tested for antiinflammatory activity (rat carrageenin foot edema test⁸) but did not exhibit any significant activity showing thereby that 2-(2-thiazolyl)benzothiazoles and their amino analogues are quite specific in their antiinflammatory activity and that the activity disappears when a thiazole ring at 2 position of benzothiazole is replaced by other N and S or O containing heterocyclic rings.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries in liquid bath and are uncorrected.

Ethyl 2-trifluoromethyl-6-benzothiazolecarboxylate (VI, R' = CF₃):

Ethyl 4-amino-3-thiocyanatobenzoate⁴ (22.2 g, 0.1 mole) was added with stirring to a boiling solution of sodium sulphide (11.7 g, 0.15 mole) in water (100 ml) and the mixture was further heated under reflux for half an hour. After cooling, any undissolved material was filtered off and the filtrate was neutralized with acetic acid. The precipitated ethyl 4-amino-3-mercaptobenzoate was taken up in ether, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Ether

was removed and the residual aminothiols was dissolved in *N,N*-dimethylaniline (75 ml) to which was added trifluoroacetic anhydride (19.0 g, 0.09 mole), gradually with stirring and cooling. The mixture was then heated under reflux for one hour. After cooling, the reacting mixture was poured into dil. hydrochloric acid (100 ml conc. HCl + 300 ml water) and stirred well. The solid product was filtered off, washed with water and treated with dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate. The solid ester was filtered off, washed with water and dried. It was crystallised from aq. alcohol, m.p. 94°, yield 14.0 g (51%). (Found: N, 4.82. Calc. for C₁₁H₈F₃NSO₂: N, 5.09%). ν_{max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹: 3080 (CH arom.); 2990 (CH₃); 1710 (C=O); 1310, 1180, 1130 (CF₃).

2-Trifluoromethyl-6-benzothiazolecarboxylic acid:

Ethyl 2-trifluoromethyl-6-benzothiazolecarboxylate (VI, R' = CF₃; 11.0 g, 0.04 mole) was added to dil. sulphuric acid (25%, 150 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux till the solid dissolved (2 hrs.). The solid, which separated on cooling, was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and then dissolved in dil. sodium carbonate solution. The sodium carbonate solution was filtered free from any undissolved material and the filtrate neutralized with dil. hydrochloric acid. The product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from alcohol, m.p. 212°, yield 8.0 g (80%). (Found: N, 5.42. Calc.

TABLE 1—1-(2-BENZOTHAZOLECARBONYL)-2-ACYLHYDRAZINES (IV).

Sr.No.	R	Solvent of Crystn.	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical data			
						Found %		Calculated %	
						S	N	S	N
1.	H	Alcohol	207-8	86	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ SO ₂	14.81	18.52	14.48	19.00
2.	Methyl	Alcohol	175	75	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ SO ₂	13.51	17.62	13.61	17.87
3.	Ethyl	Alcohol	164	72	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO ₂	12.76	16.64	12.85	16.87
4.	Phenyl	Alcohol	218	74	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO ₂	10.22	13.96	10.77	14.14
5.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	Alcohol	191	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ SO ₂ Cl	10.10	12.30	9.65	12.67
6.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Xylene	218	66	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO ₄	9.66	15.82	9.36	16.37
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Toluene	190	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₃	9.60	13.02	9.79	12.84

TABLE 2—2-(1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL)BENZOTHAZOLE AND 2-(1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL)BENZOTHAZOLE AND THEIR ANALOGUES (I).

Sr.No.	X	R	Solvent of Crystn.	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical data			
							Found %		Calculated %	
							S	N	S	N
1.	O	H	Alcohol	220	49	C ₉ H ₅ N ₃ SO	15.40	20.75	15.76	20.69
2.	O	Methyl	Benzene	155	48	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO	14.68	19.02	14.75	19.36
3.	O	Ethyl	Benzene-pet ether (60°-80°)	115	48	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ SO	13.54	18.39	13.85	18.18
4.	O	Phenyl	Alcohol	177	54	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ SO	11.20	14.64	11.47	15.05
5.	O	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Alcohol	178	60	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClN ₃ SO	10.38	13.01	10.21	13.39
6.	O	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Toluene	234	50	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₄ SO ₃	9.85	16.98	9.88	17.29
7.	O	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Alcohol	180	61	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO ₂	9.90	13.48	10.36	13.59
8.	S	H	Alcohol	152	62	C ₉ H ₅ N ₃ S ₂	28.75	19.67	29.23	19.18
9.	S	Methyl	Alcohol	167	51	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	27.01	18.19	27.46	18.03
10.	S	Ethyl	Alcohol	136	50	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	25.66	16.82	25.91	17.00
11.	S	Phenyl	Alcohol	192	55	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	22.16	14.17	21.70	14.23
12.	S	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Xylene	258	59	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClN ₃ S ₂	19.80	12.62	19.42	12.75
13.	S	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Xylene	280	54	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	18.98	16.31	18.82	16.47
14.	S	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Toluene	200	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ O	19.28	13.14	19.69	12.92

for C₉H₄F₃NSO₂: N, 5.67%). ν_{max}^{Nujol} cm⁻¹: 2750-2540 (OH); 1700 (C=O), 1300, 1180, 1150 (CF₃).

2-Trifluoromethyl-6-benzothiazolecarbonyl chloride (VII). R' = CF₃:

2-Trifluoromethyl-6-benzothiazolecarboxylic acid (4.94 g, 0.02 mole) was added to thionyl chloride (25 ml) and the mixture heated under reflux for 5 hrs. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The residual product, which solidified on cooling, was crystallized from pet. ether (60-80°) m.p. 86°, yield 4.55 g (86%). (Found: N, 4.82. Calc. for C₉H₃ClF₃NSO: N, 5.27%).

1-(2-Benzothiazolecarbonyl)-2-formylhydrazine (IV, R = H):

2-Benzothiazolecarbohydrazide⁹ (3.86 g, 0.02 mole) was added to 90% formic acid (30 ml) and the mix-

ture heated under reflux for 4 hrs. The mixture was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water (200 ml). The solid product was collected by filtration, washed thoroughly with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol. Physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

1-(2-Benzothiazolecarbonyl)-2-acylhydrazines (IV, (R = alkyl or aryl):

Acid chloride or acid anhydride (0.022 mole) was gradually added to a solution of 2-benzothiazolecarbohydrazide (3.86 g, 0.02 mole) in dry pyridine (20 ml) with stirring and cooling. The mixture was heated under reflux for half an hour, cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The white solid was collected by filtration, washed with water, dried and crystallized from suitable solvent. These compounds are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 3—1-(6-BENZOTHAZOLECARBONYL) OR (2-TRIFLUOROMETHYL-6-BENZOTHAZOLECARBONYL)-2-ACYLHYDRAZINES (VIII).

Sr.No.	R'	R	Solvent of Crystn.	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical data			
							Found %		Calculated %	
							S	N	S	N
1.	H	Phenyl	Alcohol	215	77	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO ₂	10.67	13.78	10.77	14.14
2.	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dioxane	245	85	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ SO ₂	9.23	12.51	9.65	12.67
3.	H	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Alcohol	236	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₂	10.21	13.08	10.29	13.50
4.	CF ₃	Phenyl	Alcohol	231	82	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₃ SO ₂	—	11.21	—	11.51
5.	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dioxane	268	80	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₃ SO ₂	—	10.10	—	10.51
6.	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Alcohol	277	78	C ₁₆ H ₉ F ₃ N ₄ SO ₄	—	13.24	—	13.66

TABLE 4—6-[5-SUBSTITUTED-(1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL) OR (1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL)]BENZOTHAZOLES (II).

Sr.No.	X	R'	R	Solvent of Crystn.	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical Data			
								Found %		Calculated %	
								S	N	S	N
1.	O	H	Phenyl	Alcohol	182	43	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ SO	11.45	14.62	11.47	15.05
2.	O	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dioxane	248	70	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClN ₃ SO	9.95	13.12	10.21	13.39
3.	O	H	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Alcohol	155	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO	10.64	13.88	10.92	14.33
4.	O	CF ₃	Phenyl	Alcohol	190	52	C ₁₆ H ₈ F ₃ N ₃ SO	—	11.62	—	12.10
5.	O	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dioxane	225	53	C ₁₆ H ₇ ClF ₃ N ₃ SO	—	10.72	—	11.01
6.	O	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Dioxane	237	51	C ₁₆ H ₇ F ₃ N ₄ SO ₃	—	13.88	—	14.28
7.	S	H	Phenyl	Alcohol	146	48	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	21.67	14.05	21.70	14.23
8.	S	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Alcohol	190	49	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClN ₃ S ₂	19.18	12.25	19.42	12.75
9.	S	H	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Alcohol	135	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	20.58	13.62	20.72	13.59

1-(6-Benzothiazolecarbonyl)-2-acylhydrazines (VIII, R = aryl; R' = H) and their 2-trifluoromethyl analogues (VIII, R = aryl; R' = CF₃):

To a solution of the acylhydrazine (0.01 mole) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was gradually added 6-benzothiazolecarbonyl chloride (0.01 mole) with stirring and cooling. The mixture was heated under reflux for 30 min., cooled and poured into cold water. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from a suitable solvent. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 3.

2-(1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-yl)benzothiazole and its analogues (I, R = H, alkyl and aryl, X = O):

The corresponding diacylhydrazine (IV, R = H, alkyl or aryl, 0.005 mole) was added to polyphosphoric acid (30 ml) and the mixture was heated in an oil bath at 140°–150° for 2 hrs. with occasional shaking. It was cooled, poured into water (500 ml) and allowed to stand for one hour. The product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

6-(1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles (II, R = aryl; R' = H, CF₃; X = O):

These compounds were prepared similarly as above from the corresponding diacylhydrazines (VIII) and are listed in Table 4.

2-(1,3,4-Thiadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazole and its analogues (I, R = H, alkyl or aryl; X = S):

A thoroughly ground mixture of the appropriate 1-(2-benzothiazolecarbonyl)-2-acylhydrazine (0.01 mole) and phosphorus pentasulphide (three times the weight of the diacylhydrazine) was heated in an oil-bath at 140°–150° under vacuum for 2 hrs. After cooling, the mixture was treated with excess dilute sodium hydroxide solution in order to decompose unused phosphorus pentasulphide. The solid product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from appropriate solvent. These compounds are listed in Table 2.

6-(1,3,4-Thiadiazol-2-yl)benzothiazoles (II, R' = H, R = aryl; X = S):

These compounds were similarly prepared from corresponding diacylhydrazines (VIII, R' = H, R = aryl), and are listed in Table 4.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R. for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (J.V.), to Dr. Nitya Nand, Secretary, Pharmacological and Drug Research Committee, C.S.I.R. for biological testing of compounds and to Prof. S. M. Mukherji, Head of the Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. O. R. RODIG, 'Medicinal Chemistry', Ed. A. Burger, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 3rd Edition, 1970, p. 896.
2. S. N. SAWHNEY and J. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 882; S. N. SAWHNEY, J. SINGH and O. P. BANSAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 566.
3. D. E. BARNARDO, H. L. F. CURREY, R. M. MASON, W. B. FOX and M. WEATHERALL, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1966, **2**, 342.
4. S. N. SAWHNEY and A. BURGER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 270.
5. S. G. FRIDMAN, *J. Gen. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1950, **20**, 1191.
6. F. D. POPP, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3503.
7. STOLLE *et al.*, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1904, **69**, 145, 366, 382, 474, 506; F. H. McMILLAN, F. REONARD, R. I. MALTZER and J. A. KING, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1953, **42**, 457.
8. C. V. WINTER, E. A. RISELY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1962, **111**, 544.
9. E. CAMPAIGNE and J. E. VAN VERTH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1344.